

Is Nigeria a Theocratic Nation in the 21st Century Political Space?

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Abstract

In the Nigerian political space, democracy is the only recognized system of government. All the democratic processes in Nigeria adorn themselves with the talk of God which is uncontrollably and severally used to spice up the polity. More often than not, in Nigeria, theocracy is interchangeably used with democracy. It is mind-boggling to state that the talk of God or God's phenomenon has become the pivot upon which Nigerian democracy hinges. During electioneering campaigns, prospective political candidates always solicit the help of God through prayer via religious centres to win elections. On the one hand, both politicians and onlookers always remark that God will choose good leaders for us, while on the other hand, those who rig and rigged themselves into power want the help of God to perform, retain and sustain themselves in power. Even when they underperform, embezzle public fund and lack human face, they still need prayers to move on. It is common knowledge among Nigerians to remark that we should pray for our leaders. In the light of the foregoing, it becomes apposite to heckle: is Nigeria running or practicing theocratic government where prayer God decides who rules? Therefore, it is the intention of this paper to explore all the trajectories through historical and demo-theocratic methods. To this end, the paper seeks to posit that Nigeria is not theocratic nation where God decides or determines who rules or not. If such is the case, the idea of responsibility, accountability, freewill, choice and trustworthiness on the part of humankind would have been the sole prerogative of God. Since it is not theocratic, humankind should take responsibility of which God should be excused from the democratic pains of the 21st century Nigerian political space. The paper concludes that all the Nigerian political leaders should replicate the ideals and benefits as it was practised in the Greek city state. The paper recommends that these ideals of democratic tenets should be internalized so as to avoid Nigerian brand of demo-crazy.

Keywords: Nigeria, Theocracy, Democracy, Nation, Political Space

Introduction

In the post-independent Nigerian political space, the only unparalleled and recognised system of government is democracy. The post-independent system of government has dramatically and radically changed because all the democratic processes in Nigeria wear the toga of God's talk to add condiments to the polity. As a matter of fact, some Nigerians cannot distinguish theocracy from democracy. It is appalling if not sad to posit that God's discourse or God's phenomenon has become a fundamental pillar where the litany of Nigerian democracy echoes. It is of interest to note that during electioneering campaigns, prospective political candidates always solicit the help of God through religious vendors, by moving from prayer houses to prayer mountains in order to win elections. In addition, a handful of electorates find solace in the fact that it is only God who can choose a good leader for us. Apart from the foregoing, it is also obvious that when the prospective candidates eventually win their elections, they under-perform and embezzle the commonwealth of the nation. Often times, we are urged to pray for our leaders because all authorities are constituted by God and they must be respected. It is against this backdrop that it becomes apparent to ask: Is Nigeria practising theocratic government where God, god, priest, or deity is voted for or appoints individuals to rule. Therefore, it is the thrust of this paper to explore theocracy versus democracy by situating the recognised system of government practised in the post-independent Nigeria.

Theocracy: A Panoramic Overview

The English word 'theocracy' comes from two Greek words *theos* and *kratos*. *Theos* refers to God, god, or Deity, while 'kratos' indicates rule, strength, power, force, especially rule derived from God. Theocracy, therefore, means 'rule of God', and in practice usually means that political leadership is exercised by clergy or representative of a religious group.¹ According to *Merriam Webster Dictionary*, theocracy is a government of a state by immediate divine guidance or by official who are regarded as divinely guided.² In the same development, theocracy is a form of government in which one or more deities are recognized as supreme ruling authorities giving guidance to human intermediaries.³ *Collins Dictionary* has added that theocracy is a form of government in which God or a deity is recognized as the supreme civil ruler, the God's or deity's laws being interpreted by the ecclesiastical rulers. The foregoing definitions support the fact that in the Commonwealth of Israel from the time of Moses until the selection of Saul as king, theocratic government was entrenched directly by God.⁴ Hence, theocracy can be regarded as a system of government in which priests rule in the name of God or a god. His ambition is to lead a worldwide theocracy.⁵ Since theocracy is described as a political system in which religious codes and laws of the state are one and the same, it will be worthwhile to employ Christian eye bird's view to consider the submission of Berekiah. In his words,

Theocracy is governance of the people by God, through a human agent. It is used in contradistinction from hierocracy, to denote a system of governance in which the human leader is recognized as an agent of God, particularly because of visible demonstration of charismatic leadership, prowess, rather than a mere hereditary religious leader.⁶

In the pristine state of the physical society, Nabofa remarks unapologetically that the affairs of the physical society are controlled by some spiritual agencies in the super-sensible realm. Closely linked to the foregoing is the idea that the well-being of the physical community depends upon the goodwill by the divine powers.⁷ This theocratic government as expounded by Nabofa lent credence to political scientists who have propounded that the origin of the government was based on divine theory: Divine theory traced the origin of the establishment of the human society to a Divine being, which could be either a divinity or divinities, an ancestor, a hero or God.⁸ Despite the recognition of other two territories, more preponderance has been given to the Divine theory as the first. Consequently, Nabofa believes that theocracy is also described as 'Divine theory'⁹. He appositely comments that theocracy presupposes the people's acceptance of the particular divinity's overlordship, since theocracy flourished and still flourishes if all citizens accept the power of the divine and are imbued in his spirit.

In modern times, theocracy in Christianity could only be situated within the Commonwealth of Israel from the period of Moses until the beginning of the enthronement of Monarchical government as pioneered by Saul. While theocracy in Islam in the entire religion. Islam is crafted as both religion and state. In other words, the two phenomena are not separated from each other. They are synonymous. As a result, in theocratic government, the ruler is simultaneously the head of government and religion. There is no separation of state and church and open practice of only the prevailing religion is permitted. The rulers in theocracies hold office by divine grace and conduct their affairs based on the prevailing religion.¹⁰

It is of essence to note that the main character of theocracy is that the state understands itself as being ultimately governed by God in the entire political system. In leadership, all the religious codes and authorities are applied. In decision making or taking, all the religious doctrines become instrumental. Thus, individual liberties are strictly restricted, while mutual diversity is limited. In theocratic state, leaders can easily and potentially promote religious harmony and tolerance by considering the shared values and principles of different religions. Under theocratic trademark, there is strong moral framework which is based on religious precepts. There is the promotion of checks but no balances. In theocratic setting, there is unity, patriotism, a very well organised environment; the fun of funding and total control.¹¹

Nabofa asserts triadic theocratic functions which include leadership in worship as *Pontifex Maximus* (the High priest). All priests of all the cults in the community operate under him; leadership in war and judicial functions.¹² To this end, it will not be out of place to mention countries that practice theocracy in the modern

world. They include but not limited to Israel, Iran, Saudi Arabia, Afghanistan, Vatican City, Yemen, Sudan and Mauritania. It is evidently clear that in a theocratic state, only one religion is usually allowed because of lack of diversity and tolerance. This means that people of other faiths may not be tolerated or accepted. Therefore, it is clear that Nigeria is not running a theocratic government and a close enquiry also revealed that there is no pure theocracy.

Democracy: An Overview

Democracy as a concept evolved in the Greek-city state or the *polis* around 5th century B.C. as *demo-cratia* means “rule of the people”. Democracy emerged as the government of the masses or the government of the vast majority with collective participation. Thus, this concept represented the interest of the people either directly or indirectly in the *Polis*. As a result of the Athenian civilization, in the city state, representatives at a public forum were recognized in the agora to promote the interest of the vast majority. It is of interest to note that the several dimensions came to expound the meaning of democracy and its set goals. ¹³ Suffice it to examine some scholars on the subject matter. Schmitter defines democracy as the “institutional arrangement for arriving at political decisions in which individuals acquire the power to decide by means of a competitive struggle for the people’s vote.”¹⁴

Howell posits that democracy is a political process where rulers are held accountable to the ruled by a variety of political arrangements, which include regular competitive multi-party elections and where those holding political office do not have automatic security of tenure.¹⁵ As sound and acceptable Howells’s submission on democracy seems to register, it is very difficult for his submission to thrive in African terrain. Because the idea of accountability in Africa perhaps Nigeria seems elusive, utopian and illusionary. However, Eyinla¹⁶ posits that two fundamental elements are crucial and prevalent in democracy. They are contestation and participation. He further stresses that “a polity is democratic to the extent to which the collective decision makers are selected or displaced through free, fair and periodic elections based on universal adult suffrage and where candidates freely compete for votes. ¹⁷ Madison et.al describe democracy as a set of institutions, including the three tiers of government, each of which is supposed to check and be checked by the other two, in order to maintain liberties and avoid tyranny, even of a majority against a minority.¹⁸ Considering cultural approach to the meaning of democracy, Rostow sees democracy as a problem-solving formula for power-sharing in which significant groups in society, either directly or through representative elites, negotiate from time to time over issues that are important to them all.¹⁹

Cunningham is univocal in position of democracy by saying that democracy is justified primarily by reference to individual freedom, where freedom is interpreted as ability of individuals to act on their preferences, granted that individual preferences are also influenced by social norms.²⁰ Having considered the various definitions of democracy, the most celebrated and enduring is the one given by the 16th American President Abraham Lincoln (1809-65), “as the government of the people, by the people, and for the people.” This implies total representation, full participation and flawless accountability to the people by the electors because the people are the government entrusted to the few who represent their interest at the top.²¹ Democracy, as one of the Western and developed world and parts of the developing countries like Nigeria among others. These Western and developed nations are the bastions of democratic values and tenets where they are reaping the dividends of democracy. No wonder, Abogunrin has argued without much equivocation that the modern concept of democracy includes the acceptance of majority rule, fundamental human rights and respect for the rights of every citizen. Democracy, according to him, is a method in which people elect their leader and are able to influence the policies of state and decide issues through the election of individuals.²²

The Antithesis of Democracy in Nigeria

Democracy has been defined as “the government of the people by the people and for the people”. It is a system of governance in which the rulers are selected by the popular mandate, rather than class or hereditary.²³ Thus, the democracy Nigeria has been practicing since the post-independence is a foreign system of government, not a home-grown system of government. This singular reason compelled Abogunrin to advocate that for true democracy to really thrive in any nation; its formulation and development must be influenced by the peculiarities of each nation, though the principles and objectives remain the same as found in true democracy, elsewhere in the world.²⁴ Therefore, according to him, “the democracy which can survive in Nigeria is the one which takes into account our history, religious and cultural differences before the amalgamation and independence.²⁵ Since the rulers and the ruled have not allied the fear and warning of Abogunrin, it is expedient to establish that we are still swimming in the foreign ocean of democracy, which terrain we find it difficult to navigate anytime. Abogunrin has sternly warned that Nigerian democracy is not a home grown or Nigerian made structure which can be simply transferred intact to anywhere in Africa. ²⁶ He does not hesitate to add that “any system of government which helps to promote selfish individualistic policies or programmes of development is diametrically opposed to democratic values.”²⁷

The enthronement of democracy after the Independence could be seen as the only game that could promote culture and political system in Nigeria. Consequently, a handful of social scientists such as Juan Clinz and Alfred Stephan ²⁸, Eyinla ²⁹ and among others praise democracy as “the only game in town”. As a matter of fact, the democratization of Africa has not yielded the much-expected dividend, and progress rather, Africans are dwindling and sinking democratically. In Nigeria, for example instance, since the enthronement of democracy in 1999, even at the very throes of birth, to an extent, democratic dividend, were a bit felt by the masses who were recovering from the Abacha’s tyrannic period, which Ehusani describes as the “years eaten by the locust”³⁰. As earlier noted, the masses felt a bit relieved till in 2015 when president Muhammadu Buhari took over the rein of power. Till date, things have not been the same again. Life in Nigeria has become unbearable and excruciating such that majority of Nigerians are undergoing crucibles. Even the blind and the deaf can see and hear the angst and squalor in the land. It is crystally clear that catalogue of lootings in Nigeria and the politics of the removal of oil subsidy among others have enabled the ruling class to be heavily subsidized by the peripheral capitalist system while the masses are subjected to excruciating economic pains and woes. ³¹

Many developmental scholars and democrats have described Nigeria as the headquarter of poverty and bad governance in the world. In fact, poverty has become a perennial problem in Nigeria, an endemic and a culture in Nigeria such that the political ruling class has weaponized poverty by subjecting the masses to a beggar-prone palliative of any kind in the nation. Kukah has consistently argued that apart from ethnicity and religion, the current democratic snags in Nigeria are the ruling class and the elite. The common and recurring phenomena in the nation’s polity are political violence or thuggery, electoral rigging, snatching and diversion of ballot boxes, political assassination, vote buying, insecurity and political interference as aided by the ruling class and the elite.³²

The lootings and acquisition of our commonwealth by the ruling class and their cronies have impoverished the core masses that during elections, vote buying becomes a common place rehearsal. The core masses are prompted by the level of hunger in the land to collect the money and vote against their conscience. Kukah corroborates the above by asserting that the intense commoditization of politics by the ruling and elite classes has meant that in the main, money is vital to participation in and access to power.³³ Gbadegesin unanimously agrees with Kukah when he writes that “in our own corner of the planet, all that the mob need is a few naira of inducement to make them go where the leaders tell them to go”.³⁴

It is mindboggling to establish that in the nation’s polity, the ruling and elite classes want to perpetuate themselves in power by all means. They do not see anything bad in whatever they do. They hate light and are leading the masses to Golgotha. The ruling and the elite classes misconstrue democracy and federalism and there is no general consensus of national goals and aspiration as well as alleviation of poverty of the poor masses. Kukah did not mince words when he states that the elite have not agreed unanimously on what they think

democracy entails, they are unclear on what federalism seeks to achieve. Lofty, high flouting national goals are highlighted, yet no one seems clear as to what yardsticks to test how they have helped us achieve national coercion, subsequent government continues to seek for alternatives, but were all seems to be shooting in the dark. The quest for democracy and what it posits to achieve remain largely a pursuit of the will of the wisp.³⁵ The debates have been marred by the confusion of imperception of whether liberal democracy, for example, is synonymous with popular and participatory democracy. By defining democracy only in such terms as free enterprise, multipartism, pluralism, freedoms, constitutionalism, equality, free market etc, will wrong the risk of mistaken the shadow for the substance and remaining frozen in the womb of ideology. Part of this confusion as often found expression in the polarized positions taken all the time by the dominant geopolitical or religious forces around which politics is articulated in Nigeria.³⁶

Furthermore, the triumph of capitalist is the help of the ruling class who use the commonwealth of the nation to canvass for support and initiate political transition as if the commonwealth comes from the coffer of the ruling party. The independent electoral body which is not indeed independent will in some cases, disappoint electorates especially the 25th February, 2023 presidential election. The INEC chairman, Professor Mahmud Yakubu promised a hitch free election in all tiers of government, when he went to Chatham house in the United Kingdom with the invention of bimodal machine to translate the results live at the polling unit. At the end of electoral 'evangelism', the presidential electioneering results were not translated, while the Presidential results were massively rigged with several alterations and interpolations. The electorates were intimidated at the polling units, some were attacked and manhandled. Several of the BVAS machines were snatched away, destroyed and hidden while it was announced that "INEC portal had technical glitches" to relay live the Presidential election results. In fact, it was reported by INEC that the server was hacked.

Kukah buttresses further that all political transitions in Nigerian politics would gulf billions of naira on this project by the ruling government in order to prepare the ground for their victory and continuity.³⁷ Interestingly, the submission of Kukah have been articulated by Olukosi who argues that:

Although, the arrival of the capitalist era brought about important socio-economy and political change that represented a qualitative advancement of human kind, it has neither been the ultimate harbinger of democracy, not did it banish authoritarianism for good. This is why some critics have insisted, with justification, that democracy and capitalism are different project in the history of modern world, a position which rules out the kind of automatic, organic correlations which ideologies of neo-liberalism attempts to make between the two.³⁸

Putting the two concepts together has actually ruined Nigeria, as democracy has been balkanized and its image tarnished. No doubt, Kukah again, has been compelled to observe that "if we persist in our quest for democracy, then we may be doomed for democracy".³⁹

A cursorily look at Nigerian democracy has revealed that the ruling class and the masses are confused on what is the next point of action. This has necessitated a paradigm shift from democracy to theocracy in the nation's polity. In other words, their democratic confusion finds theological expression of projecting God's talk in a democratic setting, which indicates that the Nigerian brand of democracy has taken spiritual dimension. The spiritualization of the Nigerian politics came to limelight during 2015 general elections, where a particular denomination presented a candidate in the post of Vice President, of which, strong support and solidarity were extended to him by the churches which ensured the victory of All Progressive Congress (APC). Since then, it has become a common parlance for the ruling class and the masses to replace democracy for theocracy in Nigeria.

At the wake of any political transition, prospective candidates are seen visiting religious houses, prayer mountains, camps, mosques, and shrines soliciting for prayers for victory. Even some candidates pay prayer warriors to be praying for them till victory is secured. Moreover, it is a common knowledge that both politicians and electorates always remark that God will choose good leaders for us as if God is casting lot in Nigeria. With all sense of modesty, ruling class always solicit for prayers even when they underperform, embezzle public fund and their administration lacks human face. They still need prayers to perpetuate the uncouth behaviour and

attitude. During elections, this ruling class does not only buy votes and as well rig elections in their favour, but also, they still solicit for prayer and the help of God to discharge their duties and responsibilities. It is not out of place to note that in Nigeria, it is an aberration and a crime to criticize the ruling class. Majority of the masses believe that all the constituted authorities are instituted by God or they are not man made. Therefore, they should pray for their leaders to act right. The various religious vendors of Islam and Christianity have argued in support of this. Your criticism and public opinion that would have served as checks and balances, are now considered as affronts and assault on the constituted authorities.

In the Nigerian “demo-theocratic” system, the current Senate President, Chief Godswill Akpabio has, in the place of embezzlement, kick back and inducement, decided to send prayers into the email boxes of all the members through the Clerk of the House. The subtle perfidy we are faced with in this country will lead us to more excruciating agonies and sniff life out of us if we do not rise to occasion. All these unwholesome and miasmatic situations have been further enhanced by religion and ethnicity through making the masses redundant, purposeless, subjective, clueless, rudderless and unseemly, no doubt, the subjectivity of the politicians and the masses in the face of this open rape and travesty have made them to seek the help of God when they should act right by voting out underperformed government. It has appeared to the populace subjectively that it is God who chooses leaders for the people because we seem to be inactive and less concerned in this regard. This theoretical mindset of the masses becomes nauseating and antithetical to democratic system of government in Nigeria. This paradigm shift of political ideology would make Nigeria to run aground. The fact remains that all these obnoxious trajectories perpetuated by the ruling party are geared towards suffocating the polity with their own selfish ideology and to entrench one party system.

To this end, it can be inferred from the foregoing that Nigeria is not a theocratic nation where God decides or determines who leads or not, rather ‘demo-theocracy’ currently practiced in Nigeria is emergent home-made or Nigerian made. It is crystallly clear that since 2015 till date, Nigeria has witnessed an ineptitude leadership summersault, unpopular and incompetent leaders steering the affairs of the Nigerian state. The current ‘demo-theocracy’ in Nigeria has snowballed and dovetailed into ‘kakistocratic’ government. Thus, ‘kakisto’ means ‘worst’, while *kratos* means ‘rule’, Therefore, kakistocracy is a system of government in which the worst people are in power. In some situations, kakistocracy and kleptocracy are used interchangeably to depict the government by the worst people. As a matter of fact, kleptocracy or kakistocracy promotes or proliferates weak and disorganized political system that repel competent, talented, charismatic and attractive leaders.⁴⁰ The above is the current state of Nigeria because it is a nation governed by its least suitable, unpopular, questionable, and incompetent citizens.

It behooves us to note that the set objectives, doctrine and tenets of democracy have abysmally failed Nigerians because certain elements as enunciated by Abogunrin were not put into consideration.⁴¹ Hence, the masses have decided to find solace in ‘pseudo-theocracy’ which has been crafted and patented as “demo-theocratic” system of government by them. Conversely, Socrates (470-399BC), one of the Ionian philosophers had long ago predicted the fall of democracy. We will quote him *extenso*.

Democracy must fall because it will try to tailor to everyone. The poor will want the wealth of the rich, and democracy will give it to them. Young people will want to be respected as elderly, and democracy will give it to them. Women will want to be like men and democracy will give it to them. Foreigners will want the right of the natives, and democracy will give it to them. Thieves and fraudster will want important government functions, and democracy will give it to them and at that time, when thieves and fraudsters finally and democratically take authority; because criminals and evil doers want power, there will be worse dictatorship than in the time of any monarchy or oligarchy.

The above disquisition has captured the current situation of Nigeria.

The Reality of the 21st Century Digital Space

The 21st century global world has ushered in astronomical advancement, development, inventions and innovations especially in the field of information and communication technology. This innovation has enabled human kind to migrate from analogue to digital space. Digital space has drastically reduced journey and movements and thus confined one to a particular place. Digital space, often referred to as the digital realm or cyberspace encompasses the virtual environment created by interconnected digital devices, networks and the internet. Its vast, tangible domain where digital information, content, and interactions occur.⁴² As a matter of matter, digital technologies enable the development of new industries, services, and businesses models, contributing to overall economic expansion. In another development, digital space can be seen as the digital 'locale' where young people gather, with digital places, giving meaning, memories and feelings.⁴³ More analytically, digital space depicts a platform where people perceive themselves to be when they use electronic tools to interact with other entities. In the same vein, digital space is created with the internet and its responsibilities is the agglomeration of the all the websites, apps and more.⁴⁴ The main objectives of digital space include but not limited to creating a digital empowered society and knowledge economy by improving technological infrastructures; increasing technological literacy, services, and resources, as well as creating an innovative digital ecosystem. As a catalyst for socio-economic growth, digital technology through innovation and investments has helped Nigerian economy to harness digital data, and new technologies, generate new content, and link individual.

With the establishment of Federal Ministry of Communication, Innovation and Digital Economy, Nigeria has been fully welcome to the digital economy which offers opportunities for innovation, entrepreneurship and job creation. These opportunities have been extended to banking sectors of the economy. On this digital roll, Banking sectors have digitalized their systems that individuals do have their bank verification number (BVN). This regularises the various bank transactions. Every exam agency such as Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) has been digitalised. In 2021, it became compulsory under the Minister for Communication, Innovation and Digital Economy, Professor Issa Pantami to register NIN including school children. This herculean task was embarked upon by individuals by supplying their BVN and Sim Card. Despite this level of digitalization of virtually all sectors in Nigeria, INEC is still promoting primordial, barbaric and out-moded method of conducting elections.

We could recall that Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) under the leadership of Professor Mahmud Yakubu promised the world in Chatham House of transparent election, free exercise of franchise and transmission of result live with the aid of BVAS machines acquired for the purpose, laden with the invention of INEC portal. Yet, elections in Nigeria are still conducted manually in the 21st century digital space. The 25th February, 2023 general elections were attended to with rigging, vote buying as usual, electoral intimidations and threats, violence and thuggery, snatching of ballot boxes, electoral manipulations and malpractices. This is happening when BVN could be linked with individual sim card and NIN. The implication is that INEC has spent billions of naira to acquire all these digitalised technologies, yet elections cannot be transparent in the actual sense. With the level of Yakubu's education and the extent of the digitalization of INEC portal, elections can be conducted while staying at home. This is possible when individual's sim card and BVN can be linked up with INEC portal and through this medium, elections can be easily conducted with the time frame.

Digitalization of Nigeria election will be the best thing that can ever happen a success story indeed. Suffice it to say that there are many advantages accrued to this method. First and foremost, every vote will count, it will build up the confidence of the electorates. This will totally eliminate vote buying, intimidation, threats, election violence and post-election violence, snatching of polling boxes and abduction of any kind. In addition, digitalization of general election will save cost, tenure and *ad hoc* members, it will save logistic movements and eliminate logistic problems. This will also eliminate delay in collation of results from one polling booth to the other so as to avoid electoral malpractices. With the introduction of digitalization of all elections, elections in

Nigeria will not become murderous and manipulated again. To this end, digitalization of elections in Nigeria should be advocated for by all and sundry. It is a step towards the eradication of unethical electoral practices.

An Appraisal

Our study has x-rayed theocracy and democracy and the reason why Nigerians have put the two phenomena into use at the same time. Our investigation has revealed that democracy as an alien ideology or alien system of governments does not put into consideration peculiar issues and skewed situations of the Nigerian state. Abogunrin buttresses further that for democracy to thrive in Nigeria, it must take in cognizance the history, religious and cultural differences coupled with the political development and experience since amalgamation and independence.⁴⁵ We have already been doomed by our democratic practices, while Socrates had predicted the death and funeral rite of democracy in Nigeria. Despite this prediction, Kukah strongly believes that democracy is still the alternative to coup and any other systems of government. He, therefore advocates that we are to be groomed for democracy whatever its limitations.⁴⁶ Kukah concludes that the only way to thrive in democracy and to change a bad government or correct rigged elections is not through another coup, but through another elections. The solution to a bad civilian government is a good civilian government, and no sacrifice by the civilian population must be considered too much to be undertaken in the quest for the ideal. It is this conviction that informs this attempt at establishing the linkage between democracy and civil society in Nigeria.⁴⁷

Apart from the foregoing, our excursion has shown that Nigeria is not theocratic nation, rather democratic state, therefore, the Nigerian masses should understand that the system of government in Nigeria is government of the people, by the people and for the people, not government of God, by God and for God consequently, the populace should be conscious enough to choose their leaders through the ballot box, criticise their leaders through public opinion and pressure groups through the exercise of their fundamental human rights. The electorates should stop praying for their leaders because God does not choose leaders for the masses. A leader should be chosen based on his/her capacity, character, prowess, background and state of health.

With all sense of modesty and dignity, religion and tribalism should be bottled up in the archive. God created us as moral and rational beings, therefore, we are not robots, without sense of responsibilities, freewill, accountability, blameworthiness and praiseworthiness. Since we are rational and moral agents, we must take responsibilities, and be accountable. On the other hand, leaders must accept responsibilities and should not run away from criticisms. For criticism is made to checkmate conducts and not assault. Criticism puts a leader on his/her toes and Nigerians should excuse God from the democratic pains and woes we find ourselves in the 21st century political digital space. A retrospect should be taken to the pristine nature of democracy in the *polis*, when democratic ideals and benefits were brought squarely into the city state. As a matter of fact, the Nigerian brand of 'demo-crazy' should be expunged totally from the democratic curricula and tenets. Sequel to the above is the fact that the leadership of INEC should transcend analogue era to the level of digital space where general elections will be conducted digitally and results transmitted immediately and accordingly. This will build confidence in the electorates and will totally eradicate primordial and uncouth behavioural vices.

Conclusion

This paper has debunked the insinuation that Nigeria is practising theocratic system of government. The monumental and abysmal failure of democracy have made the masses and politicians alike to resign to theocracy believing that the nation is beyond human redemption as a result of the rot. Thus, the Masses believe that our leaders need prayers and it is only God who can choose a good leader since all the constituted authorities do not escape the purview of God. This exponential contradiction has called for investigation in order to put into proper perspective the actual fact surrounding the suffering and impoverishment of the masses. Our excursion has revealed that currently, Nigeria is practising democratic system of government not theocracy. As a result of the rottenness in the Nigerian system of governance coupled with the impoverishment and lack of means to livelihood compared Nigerians to believe that theocracy is the order of the day. The impoverishment and lack of means to

livelihood employed by the ruling class have weakened the majority of the masses to the extent of not differentiating demo-theocracy from Kakistocracy. The paper, therefore advocates that ethnicity and religion should be jettisoned in the Nigerian political overboard, so as to choose right candidates rather than self-centred and selfish candidates laden with cluelessness, rudderlessness, fraudulence and incompetence. In other words, bad leaders should be voted out, while good and reputable candidates based on merits should be voted in. In addition, Nigeria as a nation, has come of age based on the level of digital space to conduct e-election. Thus, the beauty of this e-election is that it has the propensity to put a permanent halt to exponential rigging, and vote buying which are now a new phenomenon in winning elections in Nigeria. This will put an abrupt end to electoral malpractices, pre-election violence, electoral violence and post-election violence. Sequel to the above, it becomes crystal clear that Nigeria as a nation is moving towards redemption from 'demo-crazy.'

Endnotes

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